

FACTORS AFFECTING FAMILY PLANNING PRACTICES AMONG WOMEN OF CHILDBEARING AGE IN UKWA EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ABIA STATE.

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Abstract: *Background: Use of family planning service helps to improve reproductive well-being of women of childbearing age. Objective: This study identified the factors affecting family planning service utilization among women of childbearing age in in Ukwa East Local Government Area. Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional survey was adopted for this study. The population of the study was 11006 with the sample size of 500 women of childbearing age. A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted for this study which was done in three stages. The instrument for data collection was consisted of self-structured questionnaire tagged “Family Planning Practice Questionnaire (FPPQ). The reliability coefficient ($r=0.82$) of the validated instrument was obtained by correlating using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Data collected was analyzed using Statistical Product for Service Solution version 25.0. Results: The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between maternal age and family planning practice as $p<0.05$ ($p = 0.00$). The result revealed that there was no statistically significant relationship between educational background and family planning practice as $p>0.05$ ($p = 0.09$). The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between belief system and family planning practice as $p<0.05$ ($p = 0.00$). The result revealed that there was no statistically significant relationship between income status and family planning practice as $p>0.05$ ($p = 0.09$). The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between spousal support and family planning practice as $p<0.05$*

(p = 0.00). The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between access to the health and family planning practice as $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.00$). Conclusion: It was concluded that family planning utilization was influence by some socio-demographic factors such as maternal age, educational background, income status, spousal approval, belief system, and access to health facility. Recommendations were made against other that traditional leaders, opinion leaders, religious leaders and their entire community should partake in the creation awareness regarding the use of family planning service as a means of promoting and improving good health status.

Introduction

Family planning permit families, individual especially women of reproductive age to plan their way of lives without subjected to sexual and social imperatives. Family planning is the core concept for controlling the rate of population growth which go beyond improvement in maternal and child health. Family planning is the information, means and methods that allow individuals to decide if and when to have children which involve a wide range of contraceptives including pills, implants, intrauterine devices, surgical procedure that limit fertility and barrier methods such as condom (United Nations Population Fund, 2017). Family planning allows people to attain their desired number of children and determine the spacing of pregnancies (World Health Organization, 2017). According to World Bank (2013) family planning is the practice of controlling the number of children in a family and intervals between their births and serve as an educational, comprehensive medical and or social activities which enable individuals

including minors, to determine barely the number and spacing of their children and select the means by which this may be achieved.

However, family planning has a clear benefit to eliminate or subside the rate of maternal death, and the overall well-being of individual, families and the communities. Studies of Greeanga, et al. (2011) had estimated that family planning programme has raise the level of contraceptive use from 19% to 62% mostly in developing countries and reported about 75% declination in their fertility. Adherence to fertility and pregnancy prevention is said to be one of the vital healthcare practice especially the use of contraceptives reducing poverty thereby boost maternal and child health. Economic Committee Opinion (2017) reported that in 2015 the birth rate among reproductive age women reduced as low as 22.3 per 1000 women as a result of improve utilization of contraceptives. Utilization of family planning is likely to decrease the rate of pregnancy, the number of unintended pregnancy and associated induced abortions and proportion of high risk or predisposition to pregnancies,

thereby improved the maternal health and prevention of diseases. Prevalence of modern contraceptive use is likely to be high among women who are married as compared with the unmarried ones. Studies of Mohammed-Durosinlorun (2017) reported that the uptake of contraceptives use was high (38.7%) among married women as when compared to 2013 Nigerian Health and Demographic Survey, but it is low among young women who had given birth. The prevalence of contraceptive use seems to be high but differs among family type. Studies of Kidayi et al. (2015) showed that 27% prevalence rate was found among those are currently married and cohabiting. Certain factors are likely to predict the use of contraceptives among women of reproductive age. Studies of Adebowale et al. (2013) showed that the prevalence of contraceptive use was higher among Yoruba's (41.8%) than the Hausa (3.6%). Several factors influence the effective usability of contraceptives especially among postnatal women.

One of the demographic variables that are likely to deter utilization of family planning is educational background of women. The educational status as a demographic factor may influence the use of family planning among women of childbearing especially those attaining primary, secondary, tertiary and maternal education. Studies of Ejembi et al. (2015) revealed that the educational status of women and her spouse was considered to be significantly associated with the modern contraceptive uses ($p < 0.000$). That the prevalence of using contraceptive may be high with the increased

status of education of postnatal women including husband. Also, women with at-least secondary and above level status of education are eight (8) times more chances of utilizing family planning methods as compared with women without formal educational background (Ejembi et al., 2015). The tendency of using contraceptives among women is associated with her educational qualification. Asiimwe et al. (2014) asserted that the more schooling a woman has, the chances of using contraceptives. Therefore, educational status may go a long way to determine family planning methods most especially among women. The lifetime use of contraceptives was strongly correlated with the education status ($p < 0.05$) (Obwoya et al., 2018). Studies of Stephen and Enoch (2014) showed that women who are more educated than their spouses tend to use family planning methods as compared with women that are educated like their spouses. Therefore, educational status plays a significant role in family planning practices mostly among reproductive aged women. Asekun-Olarinmoye et al. (2013) reported that in Nigeria, women with tertiary educational status are one and a half times more likely to have ever used contraceptive than women who has mere secondary educational status. Ejembi et al. (2015) revealed that the educational status of women and spouses were found to be significantly associated with contraceptives use ($p < 0.000$) and the prevalence of using family planning became higher with increase in the level of education of women and their spouses. The educational status of women of reproductive age is one of the socio-demographic factors that may predict the use of

modern contraceptive. However, most women with secondary educational status and below are less likely to use any form of family planning as when compared with the more educated one. The educational status of women would determine their contraceptives use and it benefit. Palamuleni (2013) depicted that the higher level of education the greater family planning use are expected to be especially among both couples. Studies of Simmons et al. (2019), reported that women with college educational background are less likely to discontinue contraceptive use ($P=0.000$). Women who were mostly educated up to secondary level and above had the chance of using contraceptive due to the level of awareness. The more women are educated, the more chances to use contraceptives (Mohammed-Durosinlorun et al., 2017). Adeyemi et al. (2016) observed that women with tertiary education were likely three times to use contraceptive than those with below status. The educational background of the individual and family would go a long way to improve the requisite knowledge of contraceptive use thereby will likely serve as a strong predictor.

Furthermore, the age of the individual may likely influence the utilization of family planning. Most women who married at tender age hardly develop mature sense to seek for family planning service to obtain adequate information about family planning methods as compared with attain the age of majority before marriage. Guttmacher Institute (2012) reported that 30 years old average United State women uses contraceptive to attain family planning goal of two children; 99% of sexually active American

women are within the age of 15-44 have used a contraceptive method. Study of Solanke (2017) reported that more than a quarter between age 20 and 14 years became mother due to no use of contraceptives (27.9% and 41.4% respectively). However, older women are likely to use contraceptives especially after their first birth or sexual debut. Studies showed that in 2011, contraceptive use among sexually active women age 15-24 were low accounting for 34% as compared to women age 25-34 at 50% (Asiimwe et al., 2014). The demographic characteristics of contraceptive users revealed in similar studies of Ettomy et al. (2013) that, 46% (77) of non-users of contraceptives are between the age 21-30 years. The duration of age of women that is found to be sexually active which may not affect the use of contraceptive method. In a similar study carried out in Bauchi State of Nigeria by Kana et al. (2016), reported that the main determinants of contraceptive use include age mostly <35 years accounted for (OR = 5.0, $p = 0.028$). Studies of Adebayo et al. (2012) buttressed that sexually active unmarried women were more likely to use contraceptive than married women with a strong significance. Evidence showed that use of contraceptives method increases with women's age, from 4% at age 15-19 to 17% at age 40-49; also, women who were older than or the same age with their spouses had statistically significantly higher rate and with a lower level of use among women whose husbands that are older by 10 years ($p<0.000$), (Ejembi et al., 2015). Furthermore, one of the demographic variables influencing the family planning practice among married women is age. The age of women likely

have effects on their family planning practices. Younger women who are unmarried may likely use family planning methods as compared with older women that are married; example condom use. Studies of Adebayo et al. (2012) buttressed that sexually active unmarried women were more likely to use contraceptive than married women with a strong significance. Evidence showed that use of contraceptives method increases with women's age, from 4% at age 15-19 to 17% at age 40-49; also, women who were older than or the same age with their spouses had statistically significantly higher rate and with a lower level of use among women whose husbands that are older by 10 years ($p < 0.000$), (Ejembi et al., 2015). There could be a variation in the family planning practices age regarding women. The family planning practices depends largely on their knowledge of family planning. Therefore, factors like age could serve as a correlate to the use of contraceptive even among postnatal women.

Family or spousal support may likely influence the utilization of family planning service among women of childbearing. Most married women may likely relieve support regarding the use of contraceptives as might be compared to other women. Evidence showed that 65% of current married women age 15-49 years uses different contraceptive method and husband disapproval affect the use of contraceptives accounted for (11%), (Huda et al., 2017; Ferdousi et al., 2010). Women with supportive relationship by their spouse have much chance than the non-supportive counterparts to continue family planning service. The use of family planning may

be successful if the husband have the interest by providing total support such as financial, and decision making regarding the method of family planning to be used (Osei et al., 2014). Similarly, women who have good communication with their husband are more likely to use family planning service other than those who do not (Olaitan, 2011). Additionally, Kana et al. (2016) reported that 35.5% of husbands were aware of their spousal contraceptive usage; that husband's support was the major influencing factors of contraceptive uses (OR = 55.1, $p = 0.000$). Therefore, spousal supports are likely to be another major correlate to contraceptive use mostly among married women. Spousal support or approval influenced good family planning among women within the age of fertility. Husbands or spouses are fully expected to support their wives either by involving in decision making, or approve the use of family planning method, and/or aid their finances which might go a long way to improve their well-being through effective utilization of family planning service. Studies of Palamuleni (2013) showed that women whose spouses or husbands disapproves or do not support family planning service are 3.05 times less chances to co family planning service as compared with women with husband support or approval. In the same vein, women who never deliberated family planning practice are 3.98 times less chance to use family planning methods as compared with those who had discussion with their husband. Studies of Ekpenyong et al. (2018) reported that husband's agreement (84.4%) boosts the use of family planning service with variation in their

educational level. There should be a joint positive decision making between both couples regarding the use of family planning service because its huge benefit on family's economic growth. Evidence showed by Renjhan et al. (2010) indicated that the use family planning service was recommended by their husbands or spouse approval. Husband's approval of contraceptives use improves the prevalence rate of contraception. Studies illustrated by Palamaleni (2013) showed that there was a rapid increase in utilization of family planning service (34%) mostly among women whose spouse had approve of family planning and it is directly related with a joint discussion with the partner. There is increase use of contraceptives among those who had their husband support more than others who do seek spousal support or approval. Therefore, spousal support may likely predict the use of modern contraceptives among women. The study of Umar (2016) revealed that women whose spouses are involved in family planning utilization are 26 times more chances or likely to utilize family planning services. Although their non-usage of family planning are due to spousal non approvals or fear. Spousal agreement will promote family planning practices.

Access to the health service seems to influence the use of family planning methods. The family planning clinic or health facility maybe located far from the community that certain client may not have access to it. The studies of Asimwe et al. (2014) further buttressed that shorter distance to the health facility increase chance of family planning uses ($p = 0.02$). Also, older women were less affected by longer distance to

the family planning service ($p = 0.013$) as compared with younger women in reaching for family planning service. However, distance to the health facility could likely alter the accessible of contraceptive. Health facility especially family planning clinic should be at-least 5 km to community so that the members of the community may reach out for their service. Access to family planning service may be essential to safe motherhood and improves the health of the populace. Since the first sex debut with a new partner is likely unprotected, the younger women are more sexually active may likely use contraceptive. Evidence shows that the use of contraceptives was positively linked with age and increases rapid with age of the women approaching 40-44 and a slight declination in age ranged 45-49 years (Palamuleni, 2013). To further buttress, married women and souses with secondary educational background and above are eight and six times more chance to contraceptive uses as compared with their counterpart without formal educational status (Ejembi et al. 2015). Promoting maternal education and fertility education will go a long way to strengthen the family planning practices. Another factor that could influence the utilization of family planning service among the population is income status. The wealth of an individual or family would affect their family planning practices through ideation. Studies of Hussain (2011) reported that simple family (98.80%) accepted the family planning practices as compared with complex family type. The use of family planning is higher in nuclear families more than in joint families. Also, a woman that

has job shows more probability of using family planning methods than those without job. Higher socio-economic status of the population may boost their sense of freedom and decision-making process regarding family planning (Hussain, 2011). Women with little or no income status may not have interest in family planning service when compared with some of them with quality salaries or wages, good businesses or self-employed work. Studies of Palamuleni (2013) revealed that women without having children are 12.20 times less chances to use contraceptive as compared with women 5 or more. Also, family planning practice could be influenced by their occupation. Women without job or work status are 1.26 times are less likely to utilize family planning service than working class women (Palamuleni, 2013). The chances of family planning practices may be improved if their socio-economic status increases.

In the same vein, the use of family planning service may be linked with belief system as well as religious background. Certain religion and culture do not permit the use of family planning methods whereas others do so since Nigeria is an ethno-religious society of which some families holds to Christian, Islam and traditional beliefs that may affect their way of life. Studies of Adebowale et al. (2013) showed more than half of Yoruba ethnic group (41.8%) had an increase use of family planning as compared with Hausa (3.6%) that religion is a strong predictor of family planning use ($P < 0.05$). studies of Muhammed-Durosamorun et al. (2017) showed a statistically significant different between religion (Muslim and Christian) and family planning use ($P .000$).

the use of contraceptive is high ranged from 49.7% in 2008 to 54.92% in 2014 among Christians than the Muslim faithful (Aviisah et al., 2018). Furthermore, religious belief may predict the use family planning. Those who consider their religious beliefs while deciding the birth spacing methods were likely to adopt any method of family planning (Beson et al., 2018). It is plausible that some are women are religious minded in all their activities may attribute it to health care service. In Ukwu East Local Government Area of Abia State, women have not been able to utilize health care service especially family planning clinic because of their low standard of living and lack of awareness regarding the importance of family planning methods. The non-use of family planning method was observed among women of childbearing age because health care service are poorly available and highly affordable that low income people cannot obtain. It could be clear that family planning is not adequately available in the health facility for use. It is against this backdrop that this study unravels the factors affecting family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwu East Local Government Area of Abia State.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The rapid increase in population growth rate, sexually transmitted infections, and complication resulting from abortion and even deaths are public health problems. The immediate need to control population growth rate and high fertility among populace in Nigeria has attracted the interest of scholars to recommend family planning service. Increase in

family population and growth, health and reproductive issues, inability to meet the family needs were traceable to failure to consider the use of family planning service.

Family planning service have not been adequately available in the primary level of health care system because government and stakeholders were less concern about the welfare of the population. However, the variation in family planning methods by background characteristics and sociocultural status are greater among women than men. Family decision making as husband in some religions and ethnics remain the final say in the family was a major challenge in effective use of family planning. It was observed that non-utilization of family planning was due to reasons that women who requested for contraceptive are not trustworthy and infidel to their spouse. There was no continuous sensitization on different methods of family planning at the grass root level resulting into lack of understanding. Several health problems such as HIV/AIDS, hepatitis B virus infection, obstetric issues were suffered because poor use protective device (family planning methods). It was reported that lack of agreement among partners, poor understanding, non-availability of family planning methods, low-income status among others preclude women from attending fertility clinic in health care service. In spite of this, people were less concerned about poor utilization of family planning service among the population in recent time. Therefore, the researcher sought to investigate the factors affecting family planning practices among women of childbearing age in

Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study investigated the factors affecting family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State. Specifically, this study sought to:

1. Ascertain the family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State;
2. Determine the extent to which maternal age affect family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State;
3. Examine the extent to which educational background affect family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State;
4. Determine the extent to which belief system affect family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State;
5. Examine the extent to which income status affect family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State;
6. Ascertain the extent to which spousal support affect family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State;
7. Determine the extent to which access to the health service affect family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses was tested at 0.05

alpha level.

1. There is no significant relationship between the maternal age and family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State.

2. There is no significant relationship between the educational background family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State.

3. There is no significant relationship between the belief system and family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State.

4. There is no significant relationship between the income status and family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State.

5. There is no significant relationship between the spousal support and family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State.

6. There is no significant relationship between the access to the health and family planning practices among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State.

Methodology

Study Area: The study area was Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State, South East Nigeria.

Study Design: A descriptive cross-sectional survey was adopted for this study. In this study, the researcher collected data on the factors affecting family planning practices among women of child bearing age in Ukwa East Local

Government Area of Abia State and subjected collected data to statistical analysis without manipulating any variable in the study.

Population of the Study: The population of the study consisted of all the postnatal women between the ages of 15-45 years in Ukwa East Local Government Area was eleven thousand and six (11006), (National Bureau of Statistics, 2021).

Sample and Sampling Techniques: The sample size for this study was 400 women of childbearing age. This sample size (n = 400) was estimated using Taro Yamene method for a large population.

Taro Yamene formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where n = sample size

N = Total population of women of childbearing age (N=11006)

I = constant

e^2 = Degree of precision (0.5).

The sample size was 400 it represents the population and findings may be generalized. A multi-stage sampling procedures was adopted for this study which was done in three stages. Stage one: sample random sampling technique was used to select 6 political wards in Ukwa East Local Government Area from the existing twelve (10) political wards. Stage two: convenient sampling technique was adopted to select women of childbearing age since the communities are not too close to each other within the Ukwa East Local Government Area. Stage three: systematic sampling technique was used to select 40women of childbearing age with

the same characteristics of interest such as those who reside in Ukwa East L.G.A to make up the sample for the study.

Instrument for Data Collection: The instrument for data collection was consisted of self-structured questionnaire tagged “Family Planning Practice Questionnaire (FPPQ). The instrument consists of two sections: Section A is made up of socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents such as age at last birthday, marital status, level of education, socioeconomic status, belief system, while section B, may indicates respondent’s views on utilization of family planning in health care service. It was a structured based on the modified four points likert scale of Always (4 points), Sometimes (3 points), Rarely (2 points) and Never (1 point).

Reliability of the Instrument: The reliability coefficient (0.82) of the instrument was obtained by correlating the two result using Pearson

Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Hence, the instrument was appropriate and reliable for the study.

Method of Data Analysis: Data collected was analyzed using Statistical Product for Service Solution version 27.0. Descriptive statistical tools were used such as mean and standard deviation for research question one while Pearson Correlation was used both to answer research questions two to seven and all the null hypothesis at 0.05 significant level.

Results

The results of the study are shown below:

Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between maternal age and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State.

Table 1.1: Pearson Correlation between maternal age and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State

Variables		Practice	Maternal age	Decision
Practice	Pearson Correlation	1	0.40	H ₀ rejected
	Sig.		0.00*	
	N		400	
Maternal age	Pearson Correlation	0.40	1	
	Sig.	0.00*		
	N	400		

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

Table 1.1 showed Pearson Correlation between maternal age and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State. The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between maternal age and family planning

practice as $p < 0.05$ ($n = 400$, $r = 0.40$, $p = 0.00$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between maternal age and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State was rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between educational background

and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State.

Table 1.2: Pearson Correlation between maternal age and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State

Variables		Practice	Educational background	Decision
Practice	Pearson Correlation	1	0.21	H ₀ not rejected
	Sig.		0.09**	
	N		400	
Educational background	Pearson Correlation	0.21	1	
	Sig.	0.09**		
	N	400		

**Not Significant; $p > 0.05$.

Table 1.2 showed Pearson Correlation between educational background and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State. The result revealed that there was no statistically significant relationship between educational background and family planning practice as $p > 0.05$ ($n = 400$, $r = 0.21$, $p = 0.09$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant

relationship between educational background and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State was not rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between belief system and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State.

Table 1.3: Pearson Correlation between belief system and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State

Variables		Practice	Belief system	Decision
Practice	Pearson Correlation	1	0.26	H ₀ rejected
	Sig.		0.00*	
	N		400	
Belief system	Pearson Correlation	0.26	1	
	Sig.	0.00*		
	N	400		

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

Table 1.3 showed Pearson Correlation between

belief system and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East

LGA of Abia State. The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between belief system and family planning practice as $p < 0.05$ ($n = 400$, $r = 0.26$, $p = 0.00$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between belief system and family planning practice among

women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State was rejected.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant relationship between income status and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State.

Table 1.4: Pearson Correlation between income status and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State

Variables		Practice	Income status	Decision
Practice	Pearson Correlation	1	0.14	H ₀ not rejected
	Sig.		0.07**	
	N		400	
Income status	Pearson Correlation	0.14	1	
	Sig.	0.07**		
	N	400		

**Not Significant; $p > 0.05$.

Table 1.4 showed Pearson Correlation between income status and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State. The result revealed that there was no statistically significant relationship between income status and family planning practice as $p > 0.05$ ($n = 400$, $r = 0.14$, $p = 0.09$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there

is no significant relationship between income status and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State was not rejected.

Hypothesis Five: There is no significant relationship between spousal support and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State.

Table 1.5: Pearson Correlation between spousal support and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State

Variables		Practice	Spousal support	Decision
Practice	Pearson Correlation	1	0.66	H ₀ rejected
	Sig.		0.00*	
	N		400	
Spousal support	Pearson Correlation	0.66	1	
	Sig.	0.00*		

N 400

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

Table 1.5 showed Pearson Correlation between belief system and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State. The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between spousal support and family planning practice as $p < 0.05$ ($n = 400$, $r = 0.66$, $p = 0.00$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there

is no significant relationship between spousal support and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State was rejected.

Hypothesis Six: There is no significant relationship between access to the health and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East Local Government Area of Abia State.

Table 1.6: Pearson Correlation between access to the health and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State

Variables		Practice	Access	Decision
Practice	Pearson Correlation	1	0.42	H_0 rejected
	Sig.		0.00*	
	N		400	
Access	Pearson Correlation	0.42	1	
	Sig.	0.00*		
	N	400		

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

Table 1.6 showed Pearson Correlation between access to the health and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State. The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between access to the health and family planning practice as $p < 0.05$ ($n = 400$, $r = 0.42$, $p = 0.00$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between access to the health and family planning practice among women of childbearing age in Ukwa East LGA of Abia State was rejected.

Maternal Age and Family Planning Practices

The result of this study illustrated that there was no statistically significant relationship between maternal age and family planning practice as $p > 0.05$ ($p = 0.09$). The result of this study is expected because as one advances in age so as the she familiar with things and can make use of it. Mature woman can be decisive on the type of family planning to be utilize to promote and maintain good health status. The result of this study is in keepings with Ekpenyong et al. (2018) and Sarvestani et al. (2017) whose studies revealed there was a significant association between age and contraceptive method

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study were discussed below:

($p < 0.05$), also good proportion women (76.9%) with the age range 30-34 years utilizes family planning methods after regular visit to the health care facility. Umar (2016) added that contraceptive use drastically increase by age indicating that there was no significant association between age and contraceptive use ($P = 0.326$). Ejembi et al. (2015) affirmed that women who are older or at the same age with their spouses had significantly higher rates of modern contraceptive use, as compared with those of lowest level of use among women whose husbands were older by more than 10 years ($p < 0.000$). Palamulemi (2013) and Adebowale et al. (2013) concord that the current usage of modern contraceptive among married women increases with age reaching the maximum of 40-44 years and decrease slightly with age group 45-49 years also revealed that age of women was a strong predictor of family planning utilization. It is plausible that as one advances in age so there is increase in understanding in the use of family planning. Increase in age determine the extent of deciding on what to do especially in chosen health care service. There are no prior studies that contradict with outcome of the present study. Hence, age influence the family planning utilization.

Educational status and Family Planning Practices

The result revealed that there was no statistically significant relationship between educational background and family planning practice as $p > 0.05$ ($p = 0.09$). The result of this study is not surprising because acquiring good education provide one with good and requisite knowledge

and understanding about health status and how to improve on it especially knowing about family planning. The result of this study is in credence with Ekpenyong et al. (2018) and Umar (2016) whose studies depicted that there was a significant association between educational attainment and level of utilization of family planning ($p < 0.05$). Ejembi et al. (2015) and Sarvestani et al. (2017) affirmed that the educational background of women and their spouses showed a significant association with the use of family planning method ($p < 0.0000$) women with secondary school and above level of education were eight and six times more chances to use contraceptives as compared with women with no formal education. The result of this study is in agreement with Palamulemi (2013) that educational status of women is a major predictor of contraceptive uses depicting those women with no education was 1.71 times less tendency to use family planning. Olaitan (2011) added that there was a significant influence between level of educational status of couples and choices of family planning ($p < 0.05$). In the contrary, studies of Sarvestani et al. (2017) viewed that educational level and contraceptive methods had no significant association ($p > 0.05$). It is plausible because people can acquire information that would better their health from difference means order than education. Increase in educational status does not means there is rapid action taken to control and promote health status. Hence, educational status may likely to influence family planning utilization.

Belief System and Family Planning Practices

The result of the study indicated that there was a statistically significant relationship between belief system and family planning practice as $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.00$). The result of this study is required because as one's belief varies so as their understanding and action differs. The result of this study is in line with Renjhen et al. (2010) which revealed that good proportion of women who are Christian by belief accept family planning and effectively utilized the family planning service as compared with Islam worshippers. Ekpenyong et al. (2018) in their own study, good percentage of 85% Islamic worshippers tried different method of family planning to reduce number of children and spacing. Ejembi et al. (2015) affirmed that Christian is mostly in monogamous relationship having two to four children were significantly associated with increase rate of contraceptive use ($p < 0.0000$). Simmons et al (2018) and Okafor et al. (2016) whose studies indicated that family and ethnic beliefs strong affect the promotion and maintenance of health status and use of health care service including family planning. Olaitan (2011) added that there was a variability in utilization of family planning which accounted for 48% are Christians, 42% are Muslims and only 10% were traditional worshippers respectively. It is plausible because the belief system varies among people as influence the way they think and act regarding improving and promoting good health status. There were no contrary studies prior to the present study. Hence, belief system influence the family planning utilization.

Income status and Family planning

Practices

The result revealed that there was no statistically significant relationship between income status and family planning practice as $p > 0.05$ ($p = 0.09$). The result of this study is necessary because family planning service is cost effective that must be paid for before consuming the service. The result of this study is in keepings with Ekpenyong et al. (2018) which indicated that good proportion of women who earned below minimum wage are 12 times less likely to utilized family planning service and depends on their husband for assistance. Raharinjaravo et al. (2015/2017) affirmed women from low-income homes are 3.05 times less likely to meet up family planning utilization and unmet the need for the family. Umar (2016) buttressed that was a significant association between wealth quintile and knowledge regarding the family planning use among women ($P > 0.0001$). Palamulemi (2013) concord that socio-economic factors as a strong predictor of contraceptive use, women who are not working are 1.26 times less chances to use contraceptive than women who are working. Those who had not visited health facility are 1.26 times less chances to use family planning than women that had attend health facility. Sarvestani et al. (2017) in their study illustrated that socio-economic status, about (21.6%) had been employed and family income showed a significant difference among women in urban and rural women ($p = 0.00$). In the contrary, Olaitan (2011) revealed that there was no significant influence between the socio-economic status of couple and their choice of determining family planning. Apart from this,

there was no other prior study that were found contradicting with the present study. Hence, income status is more likely to constitute a determinant of family planning utilization.

Spousal approval and Family planning Practices

The result of the study revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between spousal support and family planning practice as $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.00$). The result of this study is possible because the use of family planning service is more than one person effort and tends to be decided by both partners. The result of this study is in line with Umar (2016) which reported that women whose spouses are involved in family planning utilization are 26 times more chances or likely to utilize family planning services. Studies of Ekpenyong et al. (2018) agreed that good percentage of women had husband's agreement (84.4%) boost the use of family planning service and was statistically significant with it. Renjhan et al. (2010) indicated that the use family planning service was recommended by their husbands or spouse approval in order to make rightful choice and financial support. Palamalen (2013) affirmed that there was a rapid increase in utilization of family planning service (34%) mostly among women whose spouse had approve of family planning and it is directly related with a joint discussion with the partner. Olaitan (2011) added that partner agreement and involvement had a significant influence on couples choice of family planning in southwest Nigeria ($p=0.05$). It is plausible because since family planning is not meant for one person but a joint decision with the partner

will facilitated effective use of the service. As of the time of this study, there was prior studies that contradict with the outcome of the present findings. Hence, spousal approval influence the family planning service utilization.

Access to health facility and Family planning Practices

The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between access to the health and family planning practice as $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.00$). The result of this study is expected because if the health facility is hard to reach it would affect the utilization of family planning service. The result of this study is in consonance with Mohammed-Durosinlorun, (2017) which revealed that the more closely the health care facility the more likely health care service such as family planning is utilized. Kidayi et al. (2015) added that more than half percentage of women visit health facility for family planning reason been that it was not far from their reach. Solanke (2017) affirmed that women are over 2 times more likely to utilized family planning service if it is close to their resident or place of living. Ejembi et al (2015) agreed that one of the contextual factors influencing the extent of utilization of family planning in health facility was distance to the facility. Asiimwe et al. (2014) concord that access to health care service such family planning were significantly based on the extent of closeness to the respondents and shorter distance was significantly associated with increase chances of family planning use ($p=0.02$). It is plausible because if the family planning service is easily accessible to the population especially among women when is

service less than 4 kilometer from the habitat. There was disparity between prior studies against the present finding but the difference in the result were due to design and sample of the study. Hence, access to the facility influence the family planning service utilization

Conclusion

Considering the findings of this study, it was concluded that family planning utilization was influence by some socio-demographic factors such as maternal age, educational background, income status, spousal approval, belief system, and access to health facility. There is need to improve the health care services such as family planning in order to promote good standard of living of the family.

Recommendations

Considering the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Traditional leaders, opinion leaders, religious leaders and their entire community

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should partake in the creation awareness regarding the use of family planning service as a means of promoting and improving good health status.

2. Government should organize women empowerment expand women's choices to access family planning services and decision making including reproductive health decision.

3. Strategies to improve open partner communication, and appropriate decision making on sexual and reproductive health should be established and strengthened by couples.

4. Government should make health care services available and accessible to populace to enable them utilize it adequately.

5. Couples should go for family planning counselling on methods of birth spacing and others future needs for the family.

Ethical Consideration

No ethical consideration was required for this study.

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